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Secret Agents at Campus
Mystery shopping feedback at a technical university

Leena Jarkko

Tiina Niemi

Verna Hahtola

Eila Pajarre

Kirsi Reiman

ABSTRACT

At xxx University constant feedback is collected regularly through several different channels. This feedback is the core of the improvement of teaching and services offered to students. Even if the feedback is collected regularly it is somewhat difficult to create a big picture, what is it like to study at xxx University. To tackle this challenge, and gain more insightful information on the matter, Teaching and Learning Services together with the Student Union conducted a mystery shopping exercise. The mystery shopper method has not been used in any other university before and has been

criticised not to be suitable for university setting. At xxx University the mystery shopper exercise was seen as very insightful and valuable and despite its weak points, eg. personal opinions and narrow data collection, it was seen as a great way to give more detailed but also integrated information on what is it like to study at xxx university.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Quality Assurance and Accreditation, Curriculum Development

Keywords: Mystery shopping, student feedback

INTRODUCTION

Students, teachers and other personnel at xxx University share the goal of improving the quality of teaching and learning. University's quality assurance system ensures that the quality and standards of degrees are consistently maintained. The system is based on the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) model known as the Quality Cycle that supports a systematic and continuous cycle of improvement. University undergoes an external audit of its quality assurance system every six years. The purpose of the audit is to identify the university's strengths and challenges. Despite the fact that feedback is collected regularly, more comprehensible point of view was needed. For this, it was decided to implement a research by using mystery shopper method.

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 Feedback in a university context

Regular feedback is collected from students to develop the quality of teaching and learning. Students are encouraged to provide feedback by answering queries through course feedback system and completing other surveys concerning the quality of education, supervision or student services. For example, all students who graduate with a master's degree complete a survey that explores their career expectations and learning experiences.

Student feedback is regularly reviewed by department-specific committees that also include student representatives. Feedback helps the departments determine specific areas for improvement. Student feedback is very much appreciated and helps the university continuously improve and assess the quality of education.

xxx University has implemented a range of long-term plans to maintain and enhance the quality of education. Students have the opportunity to get involved in quality assurance by providing feedback and serving on various governing bodies and committees. There is also an email-address for open feedback where students and personnel can send feedback concerning all actions at xxx University. New initiatives can be made by sending email to another email address.

2 DATA COLLECTION AND METHODS

2.1 Mystery shopper method

Mystery shopping is a well-known and widely used method to test customer service processes. It can be used in any industry but it is mostly used in retail stores, hotels, movie theaters etc. The methods can vary widely but the main idea is to use trained individuals to act as a customer and report on their experiences in an objective way

[3]. In a mystery shopping method it is possible to use professionals who act as a customer or to use actual customers who then report their experience [2]. Douglas et al. explored the appropriateness of using mystery shopping in higher education institutes and concluded that would be a long way off [1]. Especially in engineering education, where most of the faculty are engineers themselves, a method of mystery shopping is not straight forward. It raises many questions on the reliability of the data and methods of collecting it.

2.2 Data collection

The key feature of the successful project was functional and direct communication between the university and the Student Union. After the reports were completed, they were openly available in the university intranet for all staff member and students.

During an appointed six weeks period, a chosen group of students kept a diary on all services they used and classes they attended and wrote down their feelings and opinions. The main aim was to collect supplement information to complement other surveys that are ran regularly. This kind of research method has not been used in any university and it gives a new insight into the world of engineering students. It compiles students' daily activities together with the lessons, software they use in the computer classes and methods that teachers use in their teaching.

Mystery shopper students were asked to observe their daily life but also to assess the quality of teaching and learning, highlight good practices in different faculties and degree programmes and assess the pedagogical competence and culture of teaching. The data offered an insight into the world of an engineering student. For example, what the students expect of teaching and how the teachers respond to this. Students also commented on instructions and guidance on courses they were taking, as well as on the course arrangements. Diaries also offered a source of information on the culture of learning, services for students and what xxx Univeristy is like as a campus and learning environment.

After the data collection phase, the students handed in their report diaries to Student Union that put together six extensive reports, one for each faculty. In these reports, a single mystery shopper student was not recognisable. The reports offered a big picture of students' daily life but also included valuable information on details that has not been visible before. Most of the qualitative research is focusing on multidisciplinary students and universities. This research exclusively offers insights in the world of a student in a technical university

2.3 Data collection process

The mystery shopping assessment method is widely used for example to evaluate the functionality of the customer service and improving the quality of various companies. Yet, the universities have not taken advantage of this method while evaluating the services they provide or the user experience the students receive. In the method, the subjects are not aware of the assessment process; therefore they are not aware that they are being evaluated. The goal is to generate objective and independent, although randomly collected, feedback. During the pilot project, feedback was collected only during the observation period, not during the surveyor's whole studentship.

The mystery shopper students were not given detailed instructions on how to collect the information. This was a deliberate decision in order to leave room for students' own ideas and impressions. Instead, students were only advised to write down their experiences and feelings about all services they use and courses they attend, but were asked to leave out the burden of history and unpleasant experiences they may have

had in the past. Students were given “a fish-bone-model” of the quality of teaching and learning at xxx University which is seen in Figure 1 and were asked to write their diaries based on this model.

Figure 1. Fish-bone-model of quality of teaching and learning at xxx University.

2.4 The collection of the assessment group

The Student Union called for students to participate in a pilot group to assess the quality of the education and learning at xxx University. In total 46 students from years 1 to 7 applied to the group. The assessment group selected according to their degree programme and the composition of the group is seen in Figure 2.

ARCHITECTURE	6 females, 1 male years 1-4
CIVIL ENGINEERING	3 females, 3 males years 1-4
NATURAL SCIENCES	9 females, 3 males years 1-7
INDUSTRIAL AND INFORMATION MANAGEMENT	3 females, 3 males years 1-5
ENGINEERING SCIENCES	4 females, 2 males years 2-5
COMPUTING AND ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING	4 females, 4 males years 1-6

Figure 2. The composition of the pilot mystery shopper student group

The assessment group had a joint training session where the quality of education and learning process was approached with the help of “the fish bone model” as seen in Figure 1. The fish bone model was given to mystery shopper students to support reflection and the collection of the observations. The mystery shopper students were given a nominal fee of 100€ for their participation to ensure the retention and the quality of the reports.

2.5 Data collection period and reporting

The observation time for mystery shopping exercise was between 9th of February and 3rd of April 2015. This was chosen so that the observation period lasted slightly over one teaching period and it contained also an examination week.

After the mystery shopper time period, the students handed in their individual reports to Student Union. Eventually, Student Union compiled final reports, one for each faculty, from the individual reports. The reports were generated based on the following structure:

1. Teaching staff and teaching
2. Students and the study culture
3. Services for student
4. Learning environment

Individual observation reports illustrated a subjective experience of studying and learning of a student during a randomly selected period and courses at given time.

To validate the findings of the reports, the Student Union facilitated a meeting for each degree programme, where observing students from the degree programme in question collected all vital observations together. In addition to this, the groups ranked to most relevant observations in the reports and agreed on the feedback that will be in the final report. This validated the data, and the observations can be seen as common feedback and not only as individual opinions.

The final reports of the faculty-based groups were about 15 to 25 pages long and contained also observations from individual courses in addition of “the fish bone model”. These course-related comments were found at the end of the reports. The themes that were covered in the reports varied somewhat according the services and teaching methods the faculties provide and that the students need.

3 RESULTS AND FINDINGS

3.1 Main Findings

The mystery shopper students gave feedback from all the subareas mentioned in the fish bone model. Most of the feedback naturally concerned the quality of teaching. Students feel that teaching faculty at xxx University are experts in their own field, but that there is a wide variety of pedagogic skills and implementations of the courses.

Even if the students want to take responsibility of their own studies, they require clear information on the requirements to complete the courses and information on course arrangements. Altogether, the students wanted to be better informed.

There were also comments on individual courses and proposals for improvement. The quality of teaching and learning has a strong impact in the progress of the studies and the development of expertise. The utilization of technology was pronounced crucial.

Lecture recordings were considered a positive trend, partly because the traditional lectures were not considered that useful and students wanted to have more flexibility in their studies. However, there were concerns over the capability of the teaching staff to use new teaching technologies.

Observations about motivations were versatile. There were comments about the motivation of the teaching staff, but mainly the students commented on their own motivation to study. The key factors that determine students’ motivation seem to be related to the processing of the feedback during the course and the interaction with the teaching staff.

Facilities at xxx university were often brought up in the observation reports. The students felt that facilities influence greatly the fluency of the studies. New learning spaces were warmly welcomed. The university studies include more and more independent work and group work that are carried outside of the lecture halls, so diverse learning spaces are important. At xxx University, the students also spent a lot of their free time at campus, so functional social and sport facilities were experienced to be important.

At xxx University, the Student Union and the guilds have a major impact on the grouping the first-year students. The tutoring is organised together with the university and the Student Union and it is highly valued. Strong grouping among students in the same degree programme was experienced to be helpful later in the studies and also helped the integration into the academic society.

The attitudes towards gaining social skills and soft skills during studies have changed due to the needs of the working life. According to the observation reports, priority of social skills learn during studies seem to be related in social activities that are not directly related to the studies or courses. The solidarity of the student community was recognised to be very important.

3.2 Exploitation of the findings

Observations mentioned in the reports had various responses depending on the department: some found the comments from the reports familiar and had heard the same things through other feedback channels, for others the feedback was more surprising.

The attitudes towards the feedback collecting method were not unambiguously positive or negative: some felt that collecting feedback “in secret” to be strange, others thought the mystery shopping method was too unscientific, subjective and poorly comparable to be used to collect student feedback. Some departments thought that the feedback reflected the feedback received from other channels and highlighted noteworthy details. Altogether, the project brought out differences between departments when dealing with feedback. Despite the doubts, it was received positively.

Development actions in relation to the functions of the departments, faculties, support services and whole university were discussed during the autumn in 2015 in various administrative organs such as Education Council and Academic Board.

The Student Union’s board members responsible for educational affairs, the vice president for education and the Head of Education visited the departments and discussed the department-related reports and actions the departments are planning to take regarding the reports. Especially in the department meetings, the co-operation between the Student Union’s board members, Vice president for education and Head of education had a significant influence to transforming the observations into practical corrective actions.

in general the departments and faculties were using the results of the project to implement developments in their own teaching and services. However, the findings could have been exploited more widely at the university, especially in the serviced offered to student centrally.

4 SUMMARY

In general, the mystery shopper method was seen very positive. It gave new insight and overall picture of the university and what it is like to study there. Even if some people were worried about pointing out persons or bringing up some student frustrations in the reports, this was not the case. Students are very experienced in giving feedback and can do it in very constructive way. Also positive feedback was given a lot. We found the mystery shopper method eye-opening and will be re-implementing the research again but this time for students who start their studies to reinforce the first year student experience and retention of students.

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